

ANALYSIS OF THE BIPA READING-SPEECH LEARNING MODEL BASED ON THE THEMATIC APPROACH OF INDONESIAN LOCAL WISDOM FOR GRADE 7 STUDENTS

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Abstract

Teaching Indonesian as a Foreign Language (BIPA) should be designed to be contextual and communicative to effectively address learners' needs in language skills, particularly reading and speaking. This study aims to develop a thematic-based learning model that integrates local Indonesian wisdom to enhance reading and speaking skills among Grade 7 students. The research employed a development research method following the Dick and Carey instructional design model. Data were collected through observation, interviews, questionnaires, and language skill tests. The results indicated that the model was effective in improving students' reading comprehension, speaking confidence, and interest in Indonesian cultural content. There was a significant increase in students' average scores after the implementation of the model. Thus, integrating thematic content and local cultural values into BIPA learning proved to be an effective strategy to enhance students' language skills while fostering meaningful appreciation of Indonesian culture.

Keywords : *BIPA, reading-speaking, thematic approach, local wisdom, instructional model development.*

INTRODUCTION

Learning Indonesian for Foreign Speakers (BIPA) is one of Indonesia's means of cultural diplomacy on the global stage. As foreigners' interest in learning Indonesian increases, the need for contextual, communicative, and culturally based learning models becomes increasingly urgent. Learning that focuses too much on grammatical aspects without integrating cultural elements has proven less engaging and unable to develop comprehensive communicative competence. As stated by Chaer (2015), language learning should not only teach linguistic rules, but also the values and socio-cultural contexts that surround them. Therefore, the integration of local wisdom into teaching materials is crucial to improving the quality of learning, particularly in reading and speaking skills. Reading-speaking skills play a strategic role in strengthening language skills because they involve text comprehension and the ability to convey ideas orally. However, based on initial observations in BIPA classes, it was found that a number of learners experienced difficulties in understanding reading texts and expressing ideas orally, especially if the teaching materials were not appropriate to their cultural background. This is in line with the findings of Setiawan (2019) who stated that differences in cultural background can affect the comprehension and communicative performance of foreign learners. These findings raise questions about the most effective teaching strategies so that BIPA learning can accommodate the needs and context of learners.

This study aims to develop a BIPA reading-speech learning model based on a thematic approach to Indonesian local wisdom for seventh-grade students. Theoretically, this study is expected to enrich the literature on the development of culture-based BIPA learning models. Practically, the research results are expected to contribute to teachers in designing meaningful, communicative, and relevant learning for foreign learners. Literature reviews show that a culture-based approach has a significant influence on foreign language learning. Fogarty (1991) emphasized that a thematic approach allows students to construct knowledge holistically by linking concepts within a specific socio-cultural context. Furthermore, Vygotsky's (1978) sociocultural theory asserts that language learning occurs socially and is heavily influenced by interactions and the cultural environment. Therefore, using a thematic approach based on local wisdom can help students understand Indonesian more authentically and meaningfully. Based on the background, problem formulation, and theoretical study, the development of a BIPA reading-speech

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learning model based on local wisdom is a strategic effort to answer the challenges of BIPA learning which has tended to be oriented towards grammatical aspects and has not utilized the potential of local culture as an authentic and contextual learning resource.

METHOD

This research is a research and development project that aims to develop a reading and speaking learning model for Indonesian for Foreign Speakers (BIPA) based on a thematic approach to Indonesian local wisdom. The development model used in this study refers to the Design-Based Research (DBR) approach, namely a research design that focuses on designing, testing, and refining the learning model through a systematic and continuous cycle. The research procedure follows the DBR stages proposed by Reeves (2006), namely: (1) analysis of learning needs and problems, (2) designing learning models, (3) implementation and testing of the model, as well as (4) model evaluation and revision. These stages are carried out repeatedly to ensure that the resulting model is in accordance with the needs of BIPA learning in the context of international schools. The data in this study consisted of qualitative and quantitative data. Qualitative data were obtained through learning observations, interviews with BIPA teachers, and field notes describing the implementation process of the learning model. Meanwhile, quantitative data were obtained from the results of student reading and speaking skill tests and a questionnaire assessing the practicality and effectiveness of the learning model. The combination of these two types of data was used to provide a comprehensive picture of the quality and success of the BIPA reading-speech learning model based on local wisdom that was developed.

The data sources for this study were 7th-grade students participating in the BIPA program. Subjects were selected purposively based on their active involvement in the BIPA program and their availability to participate in the full model development process. Data collection techniques included participant observation, interviews, documentation, questionnaires, and reading and speech proficiency tests. Observations were conducted to assess student engagement in the learning process, while interviews were aimed at eliciting student opinions regarding the model's effectiveness. Data collection instruments included observation sheets, interview guides, student perception questionnaires, and reading and speaking test items adapted to thematic material on Indonesian local wisdom. All instruments were developed based on indicators of reading and speaking competency achievement in BIPA learning, aligned with the Cambridge curriculum. The data collection process begins with small-scale trials and progresses to large-scale trials. In the limited trial phase, the model is implemented on a small scale to obtain initial feedback. It is then revised and continued with larger-scale trials to assess its overall impact on student learning outcomes. The data analysis methods used in this study were qualitative descriptive analysis for non-numerical data and descriptive statistical analysis for quantitative data. Qualitative data were analyzed through data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. Meanwhile, quantitative data were analyzed using percentages and average scores to measure improvements in student learning outcomes and perceptions of learning.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aims to develop a BIPA reading-speech learning model based on the thematic approach of Indonesian local wisdom and to determine its effectiveness in improving the reading and speaking skills of 7th grade students. To answer these objectives, the learning model was developed based on the ADDIE design and implemented in two trial stages, namely limited trials and field trials. The results of the model implementation show that a thematic approach with local wisdom-based story material has a positive impact on student learning processes and outcomes. Reading activities become more enjoyable because students are drawn to content related to local Indonesian culture, such as folktales, legends, and traditions. Students are also more active in speaking because they feel they have sufficient understanding to express their opinions based on the texts they read.

Results from an open-ended questionnaire showed that most students felt more engaged in learning Indonesian when the texts used were culturally based. They stated that local stories helped them understand Indonesian values and customs, making the learning process more meaningful and enjoyable. These findings support theoretical studies that a thematic approach can enhance cohesion between teaching materials and students' learning experiences. Furthermore, the integration of cultural values into learning materials contributes to affective aspects that encourage engagement and motivation in learning. In addition, the results of the development of teaching materials also include the creation of a teaching guidebook containing various learning materials related to Indonesian local wisdom, including information about traditional culinary, regional games, and equipped with learning videos that can be used as independent learning resources at home. The developed reading-speech learning model also encourages students to be active, think critically, and understand the cultural meaning of language. Learning becomes more communicative and contextual, in line with the characteristics of beginning BIPA learners. Overall, this model is

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worthy of recommendation as an alternative Indonesian language learning model for non-native speakers in international schools.

CONCLUSION

The development of a BIPA reading-speech learning model based on a thematic approach to Indonesian local wisdom has made a real contribution to improving the quality of Indonesian language learning for non-native speakers, particularly seventh-grade students. This model is designed to address students' needs in understanding reading texts and conveying ideas orally in a more contextual, communicative, and meaningful manner. The thematic approach integrated with local wisdom values not only enriches the teaching material but also encourages active student involvement throughout the learning process. Through the application of this model, it was found that students' learning experiences became more positive because they felt connected to the culturally and emotionally relevant content. Reading and speaking activities no longer felt rigid, but rather became part of a fun and effective learning interaction. Thus, the developed learning model addressed the main research problem, namely the need for an effective, engaging, and culturally based approach to BIPA reading and speech instruction for foreign students at the secondary level.

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